

The Role of the Holy Spirit in Attaining a Holistic Society

Sorin Badragan, PhD

Baptist Theological Institute, Bucharest, Romania
University of Bucharest, Romania
sorinbadragan@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT: This paper claims that the strenuous task of defining the concept of “holistic society” needs to engage the classical approaches to the matter. Plato in antiquity, More in the middle ages, as well as Durkheim and Galbraith in more recent times, offer useful insights which help us identify the main characteristics of what could be termed “holistic society.” With that addressed, the paper will continue with a theological exploration of the role the Holy Spirit plays in achieving a holistic society. The Spirit creates and sustains the society as this is part of the created order which the Spirit vivifies, then it connects it to the very life of the Triune God; the Spirit also imprints His image everywhere it is present by producing His fruit and lastly He bears witness to Christ in order to turn the world (including society) towards the Son so that it participates in the eternal relationships between the Divine Persons.

KEY WORDS: holistic society, Holy Spirit, fullness, community, perfect society

The theme of this symposium is a challenging one for a number of reasons; to mention but a couple, a basic search of the phrase ‘holistic society’ on the all-knowing internet offers surprisingly few direct entries; more than that, on a puzzling fourth place, lies a New Age book, while the first three places are not straightforwardly related to our phrase. This absence can be noticed also in the

academic literature, the concepts addressed being rather the 'ideal society' or the 'perfect society'. Another motive is related to defining the concept of a holistic society and then to implement whatever presumably difficult principles and measures are needed to achieve it.

Therefore, is a holistic society possible? We will argue that it is, if by that we do not mean a 'perfect' society and if we allow the Holy Spirit to play His instrumental role in this endeavour.

In his famous work 'Republic', Plato presents Socrates outlining the profile of a perfect society which would inhabit a perfect city. Unsurprisingly, given the times when it was written, the theory of a perfectly established society evolves around the harmony between its citizens who, although belonging to three well defined hierarchical classes, accept their place and role in the society as gods' given. However, the hierarchy is not related to value or worth but to different roles within the society and these were ascribed and cannot be changed: 'Each individual can practice one pursuit well, he cannot practice many well, and if he tried to do this and dabbled in many things, he would surely fail to achieve distinction in all of them.' (Plato 2004, 78, ll. 394e) This rather simplistic approach to the way in which a perfect society could be achieved was not implemented then, and the chances for that to happen have diminished as the dynamics of a society have got more complicated and the cosmogony severely challenged.

Another well-known attempt to propose a model for a perfect society, following the thinking of Plato and echoing other classical works, but drawing on biblical narratives, was the work 'Utopia' in which Thomas More, in 1516, aimed to sketch out an ideal society; he prescribes in detail all the aspects of the society: starting with prescriptions for the design of the small towns in which the population would be organized—including measurements for the roads: 'The streets are twenty feet broad; there lie gardens behind all their houses' (More, 1516), to addressing the magistrates, agriculture and so on. In order to achieve this, the concept of money should be eliminated, property shared by the whole community and the principles and values of Christian origin adopted without the faith as such. While this work did indeed criticize the medieval societies, especially the English one, the other probable goal, namely

proposing a model to implement by societies, has failed because it is highly speculative (hence the name!) and it relies on a very positive understanding of human nature.

In more recent times, Emile Durkheim emphasized the precedence the individual has over the society which 'has for its substratum the mass of associated individuals.' (Durkheim 1953, 10); more than that, the French sociologist rejects the alleged tension between the two and argues that what he calls 'the cult of the individual' is ultimately determined by the society which is created by the individual, who, in the context of the development of industrial societies, is not oppressed anymore but freed: "Thus very far from there being the antagonism between the individual and society which is often claimed, moral individualism, the cult of the individual, is in fact the product of society itself. It is society that instituted it and made of man the god whose servant it is." (Durkheim 1953, 29) Durkheim continues underlying the goodness of the society which transcends each and all individuals who compose it, being at the same time the very basis for morality: 'Society is the field of an intense intellectual and moral life with a wide range of influence. From the actions and reactions between its individuals arises an entirely new mental life which lifts our minds into a world of which we could have not the faintest idea had we lived in isolation.' (Durkheim 1953, 29) We agree with the eminent French sociologist that the society is a good and noble outcome of the interactions of human beings between themselves, but the issue at stake is whether there can be a good or rather perfect society within itself, in what regards the quality of the relationships and of the life of the individuals within itself.

A helpful analysis came from the John Kenneth Galbraith with his rather different economic perspective combined with social and political insights. In his *The Good Society: the Humane Agenda*, he suggests that perfect society is attainable as long as the difficult task of defining it is accomplished. He reckons that a 'good, even decent society' is possible through the participation of the excluded, through offering a basic source of income to every single person—either 'through' the market (working) or by government help, through maintaining the freedom of the individual and ethnical and racial

equality. (John Kenneth Galbraith 1996, 10–74) While the economics play a very important role in the dynamics of a society, Galbraith overlooks the complexity of the human network and human nature which raise certain challenges for the well-being of a community: the self-centeredness of human beings, competition with others, the improbable moral goodness of people and so on.

In theology, the concept of a perfect society is related not only to the church or the Kingdom of God, as one might expect, but also to the state; drawing heavily on Aristotle, Thomas Aquinas spoke of the state as *communitas perfecta* in the sense that it has capacity to fulfill the *telos* for all its parts and can enforce the law. (Thomas Aquinas, *Summa Theologiae*, Ia–IIae, q. 90) While one could argue that church triumphant can be regarded as *communitas perfecta* in itself, church militant is struggling to be that. Even the social gospel theologian Walter Rauschenbusch, with his optimistic understanding of the unveiling of Kingdom in the present world, admits that *communitas perfecta* is not fully reachable before the eschaton, but he challenges the people to strive to actualize that as much as possible: ‘We shall never have a perfect life, yet we must seek it with faith. At best there is always an approximation to a perfect social order. The Kingdom of God is always but coming. But every approximation of it is worth while.’ (Rauschenbusch 1907, 77)

In 1893, Washington Gladden emphasized the instrumental role played by the internal regeneration of the individual in order to achieve the transformation of the society; as a matter of fact, the relationship is one of conditionality: ‘the end of Christianity is twofold, a perfect man in a perfect society. These purposes are never separated; they cannot be separated. No man can be redeemed and saved alone; no community can be reformed and elevated save as the individuals of which it is composed are regenerated.’ (Gladden 2004 [1893], 1)

A proposal for a holistic society as such came from Popescu and Stanciu who coin the phrase ‘ecolonomic society’ which, in the understanding of the authors, requires a new mindset and a new life style as perceptive human beings, led by true wisdom to an accomplished existence in the context of the wider community with all its complex relationships. (Popescu, Stanciu 2015, 68)

The argument is not very convincing as it does seem utopian and descriptive, but it does indeed confirm the main aspects of what scholars consider to be the fundamental issues of a holistic society.

So far we have actually looked at various aspects of what makes a society function at its fullest potential, which could be termed 'good', 'perfect' or 'holistic'. If it were to distinguish between these labels, especially between the last two, the first would focus on the excellence of the network of the society itself, while the latter evolves around the individual—the society is 'holistic' inasmuch it fully addresses the needs of the individual, that is, it does that in a 'holistic way'—taking into account the relationship with the other individuals, with the groups, with the institutions, the economic, political and spiritual condition. In the end, when a society manages to fully do that, 'holistic' equals 'perfect'.

In what follows we aim to explore the role which the Holy Spirit plays in making a society be holistic; taking into consideration the main aspects of the work of the third divine Person, we will evidence the its fundamental part in the forming, preserving and the development of a holistic society.

The work of the Holy Spirit towards a holistic society

It is not the goal of our paper to present the complex work of the Spirit in its entirety, but to mention the facets which are relevant to the society. In a sense, from an economical perspective of the Trinity, everything which happens in the current era of human existence is in the 'dispensation' of the Holy Spirit. But the Spirit does that in a particular, special way; the British scholar Paul Fiddes points to the self-effacing of the Spirit in what regards the relationship with the Father and the Son (the foretold goal of glorifying them—John 16: 12–15), on the one hand and in what regards the work the Spirit is doing in us and in the created world. (Fiddes 2000, 259–261) It is not therefore surprising that the Spirit has been associated primarily with the work within the individual and corporative Christian life: the sanctification of the believers and the constitution and the functioning of the church; Lederle warns not to minimize the ministry

of the third divine Person: ‘The Spirit is at work in the world and should not be degraded to an ornament of piety.’ (Lederle 1988, 338)

The Spirit creates and sustains life

The creation is ontologically different but related to the Trinity; it came into existence precisely in the context of the overflowing relationships of love between the Three. It was by the power of the Holy Spirit that the creation came *ex nihilo* and it is by the same power that it does not return to nothingness. The Spirit vivifies the whole creation (Psalm 104: 29, 30) so any talk about human life must start there. As Pinnock rightly reminded us, the omnipresence of God is actually the omnipresence of the Spirit who has a ‘cosmic duty’ in carrying the creational and redemptive goals of God (Pinnock 1996, 51, 53)

The Spirit generates community

In more recent times, there has been a daring step taken by some theologians in rejecting the classical thesis of the absolute simplicity in the being of God; one of these courageous scholars was Pinnock who rightly suggested that this understanding was adopted uncritically by the first generations of theologians from the greek philosophy and instead he concluded, based on the revelation, that we can understand God as a plurality of Persons in an ontological unity. (Pinnock 1996, 32–35) The influential explanation of the nature and the role of the Spirit within the Trinity offered by Augustine supports the view Pinnock voiced that the Spirit is *vinculum amoris*, the bond of love between the Father and the Son, not as an impersonal intermediary, but as an equally dignified divine Person. (Augustine, *On the Holy Trinity*, 15: 17–19). So by His very nature, the Spirit connects persons, actualizing the capacity of the human beings who are created in the image of God. He does that exactly how he is in his being, as a *vinculum amoris*, which means the Spirit creates a community of love—it is not only the church, as Augustine rightly emphasized, but any community of beings. In this sense, the divine community is a

model to be implemented by the human beings who yet fail to do that thoroughly; at the same time, it must be added that this is not to be done by imitating 'from distance', but by participation in the life of the Triune God. Of the theologians we have engaged with so far, this important point is repeatedly made by Fiddes and Pinnock who speak of our participation in the movements between the Three divine Persons. (Fiddes 2000; Pinnock 1996)

The Spirit connects the community to God

Drawing on Irenaeus, Pinnock points that the creation comes to be within the relationship of love between the Father and the Son through the work of the Holy Spirit; this means that while creation is distinct to God in what regards its nature, it is not outside God, but inside Him. (Pinnock 1996, 58) It can therefore be said that everything is in God by being held by the Spirit who eternally connects the Father and the Son. The implication is that the Spirit can make the society participate in the life of God, this being one of the profound ways to experience fullness in all aspects of its life, to be 'holistic' in the truest sense. This, of course, requires the consent of the society as such; the society is somewhere in the complex relationships between the Father and the Son, but the richness, fullness are experienced inasmuch we open ourselves as individuals and communities to the being of God.

This is especially relevant in the contemporary Western world which has accepted the secularization uncritically, even more, as if this is genuine progress in the development of humankind. While human beings with all their networks are treated as being free by God, they are all under God, for nothing cannot *not* be under Him. By not accepting this, the society resists God, it denies itself the wholeness it could experience by opening itself to Him.

The Spirit produces His fruit within the community (society)

In a well-known passage, Galatians 5: 22, 23, apostle Paul speaks of the 'fruit' the Spirit produces—of the nine values, only one, joy,

is not directly related to life-together, though it often springs out of our relationships. The Spirit, overflowing with love and being perfect only as God can be, produces His fruit not only in the life of the regenerated individuals, that is the ones who have accepted the spiritual renewal effected by the Spirit, but everywhere the Spirit is. This can, actually must be experienced in the families of the spiritually regenerated, in the church which is constituted and inhabited by the Spirit, but also in any community. Life together in the society would be impossible if the Spirit does not, in often times hidden way, mesh together the fundamental values which are implemented within the complex network of the wider community: love, peace, goodness, faithfulness and so on. This is because God has not abandoned this world but continues to pursue His creative and redemptive goals with it, as we mentioned above.

The Spirit bears witness to Christ

In order to fulfil its destiny, the world needs to turn towards Christ and open up itself to accept His rule and experience the plenitude of the fellowship with the Triune God. It is the Spirit who confronts the world with the imperative to submit itself to the King of all, so that the Kingdom of God is actualized. The Spirit glorifies Christ (John 16: 13–15) and works within the world towards yielding to Him. Without this endeavour, the society cannot experience wholeness, for it rejects its destiny. Accepting the witness of the Spirit will not transform society into the church, for the two although overlap in some areas, they are divinely projected to serve different areas of human life. Instead the Kingdom will ‘come’, the will of the Father will be done on earth as it is in heaven, so the Kingdom will be more thoroughly manifested.

Conclusion

A holistic society is, theoretically, a possible project for it does not mean to be a perfect society—this latter state will be achieved in

the *eschaton*. A society can experience wholeness only by connecting itself to the life-giving Spirit, who created it, who sustains it and works towards drawing it into the sublime eternal divine relationships.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Aquinas, Thomas, *Summa Theologica*. South Yarra, Australia: Leopold Classical Library, 2015.
- Durkheim, Emile, *Sociology and Philosophy*, London: Cohen and West Ltd. Routledge Revivals, Taylor & Francis Group, 1953.
- Fiddes, Paul S. *Participating in God. A Pastoral Doctrine of the Trinity*, Louisville, Kentucky: Westminster John Knox Press, 2000.
- Gladden, Washington, *Tools and Man. Property and Industry under the Christian Law*, Eugene, Oregon: Wipf and Stock Publishers, 2004.
- Lederle, H. I. *Treasures Old and New: Interpretations of Spirit-Baptism in the Charismatic Renewal Movement*, Peabody, Mass.: Hendrickson, 1988.
- More, Thomas, 1516, *Utopia*. http://history-world.org/Utopia_T.pdf (Accessed on November 12, 2017)
- Plato, *Republic*, Indianapolis: Hackett Pub. Co., 2004.
- Popescu Constantin and Stanciu Vasile Miltiade, 2015. 'A Holistic vision of an economic society, www.nos.iem.ro (Accessed on November 12, 2017)
- Rauschenbusch, Walter, *Christianity and Social Order*. New York: The Macmillan Company, 1907.